

ANATOMY OF NEUROTRANSMITTERS AND THEIR INFLUENCE ON BEHAVIOR

Avezov Olmos Ravshanovich¹

Associate Professor of

Shavkatova Shakhnoza Pulot qizi²

Student of

¹Bukhara State Pedagogical Institute

²Bukhara State University

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ANNOTATION

The article provides information about the anatomical structure, function and working mechanisms of neurotransmitters. Types of neurotransmitters, their effects on our physical and mental functioning, and the effects of other chemicals on neurotransmitters are discussed.

Key words: Neurotransmitter, neuron, axon, synapse, amino acid, endorphin, morphine, Alzheimer's, acetylcholine, dopamine, demotivation, depression.

INTRODUCTION

A neurotransmitter is a chemical substance that transmits information from one nerve cell (neuron) to another by crossing the space between cells, the synapse. Neurotransmitters are chemicals that travel from neuron to neuron and transmit impulses to muscle cells and other cells. More precisely, neurotransmitters are a means of sending signals from one part of the body to another. More than 100 neurotransmitters are known to us. Most of them are composed of amino acids and other complex compounds.

MAIN PART

The receptors and muscles have the ability to contract. If the transmission of ACh neurotransmitters is blocked, as in some types of anesthesia, the muscles cannot contract and the person can become paralyzed.

Candace Pertand Snyder (1973), who made the sensational discovery about neurotransmitters, attached a radioactive substance to morphine. This substance has been used in areas related to mood and pain. Our neurotransmitter molecules are released in response to pain and vigorous exercise. These endorphins (short for endogenous morphine) may help explain the feel-good effects of what we now call the "runner's high," the pain-relieving effects of acupuncture, and the insensitivity to pain in some severely injured people.

SOME NEUROTRANSMITTERS AND THEIR FUNCTIONS		
Neurotransmitter	Function	Examples of Malfunctions
Acetylcholine (ACh)	Enables muscle action, learning, and memory.	With Alzheimer's disease, ACh-producing neurons deteriorate.
Dopamine	Influences movement, learning, attention, and emotion.	Excess dopamine receptor activity is linked to schizophrenia. Starved of dopamine, the brain produces the tremors and decreased mobility of Parkinson's disease.
Serotonin	Affects mood, hunger, sleep, and arousal.	Undersupply linked to depression. Prozac and some other antidepressant drugs raise serotonin levels.
Norepinephrine	Helps control alertness and arousal.	Undersupply can depress mood.
GABA (gamma-aminobutyric acid)	A major inhibitory neurotransmitter.	Undersupply linked to seizures, tremors, and insomnia.
Glutamate	A major excitatory neurotransmitter; involved in memory.	Oversupply can overstimulate brain, producing migraines or seizures (which is why some people avoid MSG, monosodium glutamate, in food).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Due to the lack of the following neurotransmitters, various diseases can occur. For example, Alzheimer's disease is associated with a lack of acetylcholine in certain areas of the brain. Loss of dopamine in certain parts of the brain causes the muscle stiffness that is characteristic of Parkinson's disease. Too much glutamate can be difficult for the brain to control because it can overexcite cells. If the balance of noradrenaline is disturbed, the appearance of mood disorders, spontaneous smoking, divorce, demotivation, depression, decreased libido. In order to prevent the occurrence of these diseases or to treat the disease, it is necessary to maintain the amount of amino acids in moderation. Our daily food should be rich in amino acids that are lacking in the body.

CONCLUSION

In summary, neurotransmitters are chemical fluids in the body, and each neurotransmitter is designed to perform different functions. They provide alternation, i.e. permanence, in the body. If the amount of this chemical is not sufficient, we cannot react to stimuli, signals do not arrive in time, and responses to signals do not arrive in time. Therefore, it is necessary to keep proteins in our daily food in moderation.

References:

1. Mayers book "Psychology" page 67-71
2. Z. Ibodullayev "Medical psychology"
3. L. Sultonova "Psychology" methodical manual
4. B. Umarov "Psychology"
5. H. G'aniyaeva "Psychodiagnostics"
6. Y. Fayziyev, E. Eshboyev "General and medical psychology"

7. <http://www.wikipedia.org>
8. <http://www.ziyonet.uz>
9. www.natlib.uz
10. www.fikr.uz

